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ЗНАЧЕНИЕ АУТЕНТИЧНЫХ МАТЕРИАЛОВ В РАЗВИТИИ СОЦИОКУЛЬТУРНОЙ КОММУНИКАТИВНОЙ КОМПЕТЕНЦИИ ПРИ ОБУЧЕНИИ АНГЛИЙСКОМУ ЯЗЫКУ СТУДЕНТОВ ВТОРОГО КУРСА УНИВЕРСИТЕТА

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THE IMPORTANCE OF AUTHENTIC MATERIALS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF SOCIOCULTURAL COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE IN TEACHING ENGLISH TO SECOND-YEAR UNIVERSITY STUDENTS

Аннотация:

Развитие социокультурной коммуникативной компетенции является критически важным аспектом преподавания английского языка как иностранного, особенно для студентов второго курса, которые переходят от базовых языковых навыков к продвинутому уровню владения языком. В этой статье рассматривается важнейшая роль аутентичных материалов, созданных для носителей языка, в развитии социокультурной коммуникативной компетенции, уделяя особое внимание их применению в преподавании английского языка студентам второго курса. Аутентичные материалы знакомят учащихся с использованием реального языка, предоставляя ценные сведения о культурных нормах, идиоматических выражениях и прагматических аспектах общения. Включая эти ресурсы в класс, преподаватели могут создать более захватывающую и значимую среду обучения, которая устраняет разрыв между теоретическим обучением языку и практическим применением. В статье подчеркивается преобразующая роль аутентичных материалов в оснащении учащихся навыками, необходимыми для уверенного ориентирования в разнообразных культурных и социальных контекстах.

Abstract:

Developing sociocultural communicative competence is a critical aspect of teaching English as a foreign language, particularly for second-year university students transitioning from foundational language skills to advanced proficiency. This article explores the critical role of authentic materials created by native speakers in promoting socio-cultural communicative competence, focusing on their application in teaching English to second-year university students. Authentic materials expose learners to real-world language use, providing valuable insights into cultural norms, idiomatic expressions, and pragmatic aspects of communication. By incorporating these resources into the classroom, educators can create a more immersive and meaningful learning environment that bridges the gap between theoretical language instruction and practical application. The article concludes by emphasizing the transformative role of authentic materials in equipping learners with the skills needed to navigate diverse cultural and social contexts confidently.

Keywords: Authentic materials, sociocultural communicative competence, English language teaching, second-year university students, cultural awareness, real-world language use.

Ключевые слова: Аутентичные материалы, социокультурная коммуникативная компетентность, преподавание английского языка, студенты второго курса университета, культурная осведомленность, использование реального языка.

Introduction. Language learning goes beyond acquiring grammatical accuracy or expanding vocabulary in the modern globalized world. It encompasses the ability to use language appropriately in diverse sociocultural contexts, a skill referred to as sociocultural communicative competence. This skill is essential for university students, particularly second-year learners, as they navigate the transition from foundational language knowledge to more advanced and real-world applications. Sociocultural communicative competence prepares them for academic exchanges, professional opportunities, and effective cross-cultural communication. This stage of learning is ideal for integrating au-

thentic materials that foster these competencies. Authentic materials—texts, media, and resources created for native speakers—serve as invaluable tools for developing sociocultural communicative competence, offering learners insights into the cultural and linguistic nuances of real-life communication. By exposing learners to real-world language use, these materials enhance linguistic proficiency and foster cultural awareness and adaptability.

Sociocultural communicative competence integrates linguistic (the ability to use grammar, vocabulary, and pronunciation effectively), sociolinguistic (understanding the social rules of language, such as politeness, formality, and cultural appropriateness),

discourse (the ability to construct coherent spoken or written texts), and intercultural competencies (the skill to navigate and interpret cultural differences), enabling learners to use language appropriately in different sociocultural contexts. Developing this competence is crucial for second-year university students preparing for academic and professional environments requiring intercultural communication.

Authentic materials are materials taken from original sources, characterized by natural lexical content and grammatical forms, situational adequacy of the language means used, illustrate cases of authentic word usage, and which, although not specifically intended for educational purposes, can be used in teaching a foreign language. These can be news, films, advertisements, songs, interviews, social networks, texts from blogs, and other materials that display living language in its natural form. Authentic materials are important in the learning process, as they show the language in the context of real situations and topics, not only in the form of dry texts prepared specifically for educational purposes.

Many scientific studies are devoted to uncovering the essence of authentic materials and their use in practical teaching. Researchers like Voronina G.I., Milrud R.P., Nonosovich E.V., A. Gilmore, Jack C. Richards, B. Tomlinson, W. Guariento, and J. Morley, among others, have addressed this issue. Based on the reviewed materials, it can be concluded that both domestic and foreign methodologists provide a unified definition of authentic materials: "Authentic materials are materials that can be used with students in the classroom and that have not been altered in any way for students learning English as a foreign language. An obvious example would be a newspaper article written for native English speakers."

The methodologists also agree in their works that working with authentic materials helps increase communicative motivation in learning a foreign language and provides opportunities to be exposed to the natural atmosphere of the target language."

Currently, there are several approaches to understanding authentic materials. For example, E.V. Nosonovich and R.P. Milrud believe a foreign language should be studied using authentic materials. Authentic materials are "materials taken from original sources and not intended for educational purposes" [7]. At the same time, the authors subdivide authentic materials into academic and methodological authenticity.

Alexander Gilmore defines authentic materials as "texts created to fulfill some social purpose in the language community" and not intentionally produced for classroom use. The author emphasizes the role of authentic materials in representing genuine language use [2].

Brian Tomlinson highlights the role of authentic materials in improving learners' exposure to natural language patterns, defining them as "texts or recordings created by native speakers for real-life communication purposes rather than pedagogical objectives" [8].

Authentic materials as a means of developing socio-cultural competence. Sociocultural competence

is a person's ability to understand and adequately respond to another country's social and cultural characteristics. It is important to realize that mastering a language is not limited to knowing its grammar rules and vocabulary. Still, it includes the ability to perceive and interpret the cultural characteristics, traditions, and communication norms inherent to native speakers.

Authentic materials such as original texts, videos, audio, and other sources used in real life are powerful tools for developing these skills. They reflect the language's lively, informal form, showing how expressions, idioms, slang, and cultural contexts are used in real situations. Using them allows students to learn vocabulary and grammar and understand how these elements function in real communicative contexts.

The Role of Authentic Materials in the Development of Sociocultural Competence. Sociocultural communicative competence includes not only knowledge of the language but also an understanding of the cultural norms, traditions, and values characteristic of native speakers. Firstly, authentic materials allow students to get acquainted with the real culture of English-speaking countries. They can see how native speakers react to different situations, their expressions in various contexts, and how cultural differences affect communication. For example, analysing American or British news can help students understand what topics are relevant to English-speaking societies. At the same time, films and TV series provide a deeper understanding of people's daily lives and behavior in these countries.

Secondly, using authentic materials helps students learn vocabulary and understand how it is used in everyday speech. Students can learn slang, idioms, and expressions not found in textbooks but actively used in everyday speech by native speakers. This helps develop communication skills in real situations.

Moreover, when working with authentic materials, students often encounter cultural differences that require reflection and analysis. For example, watching a film that reflects the traditions of another country can encourage students to think about how culture influences behavior and perceptions of the world. Analysing news from different sources helps develop a critical attitude toward information and understand how political and cultural contexts can influence the presentation of events.

Last, but not least, authentic materials make learning more interesting and dynamic. Students feel they are learning theoretical rules and the language they will use in real life. Films, songs, podcasts, or popular blogs help establish a connection between the educational material and students' interests, which helps increase motivation for learning.

Authentic materials improve language proficiency and foster cultural understanding, critical thinking, and practical communication skills. They help bridge the gap between classroom learning and real-life application, making them an invaluable tool in language teaching. Below is a detailed explanation of these benefits:

1. Developing Critical Thinking and Analytical Skills. Authentic materials, especially from modern

sources such as news articles, interviews, or social media, require students to understand the text and critically evaluate the information presented. For example, watching news in English helps students analyze how different cultural and political contexts affect the presentation of information, which contributes to a deeper understanding of international issues.

2. Enhanced Real-World Relevance. Authentic materials allow students to get acquainted with real life in English-speaking countries and understand how society functions, not just theoretically. For example, using films, TV series, advertising, or social media allows you to see how English speakers react to different situations, what topics are important to them, and what cultural codes are present in everyday life.

3. Increased Motivation and Engagement. Learners are generally more motivated when they see the practical application of their learning. Authentic materials, being interesting and relatable, captivate students' attention better than artificial, textbook-only content. Using popular songs, video blogs, or memes helps to connect the material being studied with students' interests, making learning more relevant and closer to real life.

While authentic materials offer many benefits, they can also present challenges, such as the complexity of language or unfamiliar cultural references. These obstacles can be addressed through careful selection of materials, appropriate scaffolding, and the design of engaging, level-appropriate activities that focus on key linguistic and cultural diversity. Being implemented thoughtfully, authentic materials create a dynamic and meaningful learning environment that motivates students and enhances their overall communication skills.

Role-playing with travel brochures is an example of a classroom activity that uses real materials to foster socio-cultural communicative skills. This activity aims to practice speaking and sociolinguistic competence in real-life scenarios. The teacher provides students with travel brochures from English-speaking countries. Students role-play asking about recommendations or booking a trip. The use of polite phrases, tone, and culturally appropriate behavior will be the main focus of the lesson. Based on the idea that authentic materials offer insights into cultural norms, values, and etiquette in English-speaking countries, sociocultural competence activities increase cultural awareness and sensitivity as well as communicative adaptability to various social contexts.

How can teachers use authentic materials effectively?

To use authentic materials effectively, teachers need to consider several aspects. First, it is crucial to choose authentic materials that match the linguistic abilities of your students to avoid frustration or disengagement. Resources with relatively complicated language, including streamlined news articles, clear-spoken podcasts, or subtitled films, should be considered for second-year university students. Without experiencing an excessively challenging language barrier, students must comprehend and become proficient in the materials.

Second, teachers should help students understand the cultural context, which may not be clear without explanations. Some cultural elements or historical aspects may be challenging to comprehend without explanations. The teacher should explain the cultural specifics mentioned in the materials.

Third, it is necessary to create a classroom environment where students are willing to discuss cultural differences, share their opinions, and learn from each other. In addition to providing a secure environment for students to ask questions, discuss ideas, and express their cultural perspectives, teachers can foster curiosity and open-mindedness in their students when they are studying foreign cultural material. This helps students become better communicators. Teachers can assist students in developing practical language skills and sociocultural competence by carefully choosing, modifying, and incorporating real resources into their classes.

In conclusion, developing sociocultural communicative skills in second-year university students requires the implementation of authentic materials. These tools help students close the gap between theory and practice by introducing them to real-world language and cultural contexts. Teachers play a pivotal role in curating and implementing authentic materials, ensuring they meet students' linguistic and cultural needs. Ultimately, using authentic materials equips students with the tools they need to communicate effectively in a globalized society.

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